

Performance Analysis and Petascaling Enabling of GROMACS

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Abstract

The work aims at evaluating the performance of GROMACS on different platforms and determine the optimal set of conditions for given architectures for petascaling molecular dynamics simulations. The activities have been organized into three tasks within PRACE project: *(i)* Optimization of GROMACS performance on Blue Gene systems; *(ii)* Parallel scaling of the OpenMP implementation; *(iii)* Development of a multiple step-size symplectic integrator adapted to the large biomolecule systems. Part of the results reported here has been achieved through the collaboration with ScalaLife project.

1. Introduction

GROMACS is a versatile package for performing classical molecular dynamics, i.e. for simulating the Newtonian equations of motion for systems with hundreds to millions of particles. It is primarily designed for biochemical molecules like proteins, lipids and nucleic acids which have many complicated bonded interactions, but since GROMACS is proved to be fast at calculating the nonbonded interactions (that usually dominate simulations) many groups are also using it for research on non-biological systems, e.g. polymers. The software is also developed within the ScalaLife project with focus on protein and nucleic acid systems. GROMACS has many active developers and a very large life-science user community.

Molecular-dynamics simulations provide reliable information about the microscopic behavior of the investigated systems by numerical solution of their equations of motion. The constant increase in computer performance (mainly due to the increase in the number of computing cores) makes a wider range of research topics – and systems – accessible to computer simulation. The increasing size and complexity of the investigated objects presents considerable challenges to the existing algorithms not only because of the exploding computation requirements but also because of the poor scalability with the number of the processors employed. Thus, the general goal of the project was to enable GROMACS to petascale simulations by identifying the main reasons for its performance deterioration and designing dedicated actions to overcome them.

An important feature of all MD simulations is the Hamiltonian nature of the investigated dynamics, which includes preserving the phase volume and reversibility with respect to time. It is favorable if the algorithms in use incorporate

these features adequately. A substantial difficulty when numerically calculating the trajectories of complex molecular systems is associated with the fact that the latter consist of both fast and slow changing degrees of freedom. The fastest motion determines the typical timescale of the processes and hence restricts the time step used in the calculation. One possibility to improve the performance of the MD simulation packages, in particular of GROMACS, is to employ multiple time-step integration algorithms which can allow longer time steps for more slowly varying forces, such as in the calculation of full electrostatics [1]. Limitations on the step size in this kind of integrators are severe, and are mostly due to stability rather than accuracy. This task is by far not trivial, due to various reasons, e.g. the effective linearization in case of semi-implicit symplectic integrators (which gain speed over implicit ones), which leads in general to loss of symplecticity and hence to unsatisfactory stability of results from long simulations. An additional advantage of the symplectic algorithms with variable time step is non-occurrence of artifacts like fake resonances and the better sampling of phase space, however, at higher computational cost. However, the symplecticity of a given fixed step size method is not automatically preserved when a variable step size is applied, also its accuracy might suffer. On the other hand, the ideas of the composition methods and splitting methods, with the specifics of the large systems subject to MD simulations taken into account, offer some possibilities for overcoming these difficulties.

The work on GROMACS in the scope of PRACE project has been concentrated on performance analysis of GROMACS software on different platforms, efficient reduction of arrays over threads (required for many codes when combining MPI and threads), topology aware MPI communicators, development of a multiple step-size symplectic integrator adapted to the large biomolecule systems and data I/O optimization in Global Arrays Toolkit.

These results have been combined with the achievements reached within the ScalaLife project where the focus has been on protein and nucleic acid systems in GROMACS. The work has been mainly done to improve the particle-mesh Ewald electrostatics algorithm. This is usually the part that limits parallel scaling, as it involves global communication over a large part of the MPI processes involved in the calculation, usually involving all compute nodes. Communication patterns have been improved, as well as a first version of combined MPI+thread parallelization. This combined parallelization is at this moment somewhat complex to set up and the work is going on in ScalaLife on simplifying and automating this. The combined parallelization already includes a few improvements from analysis of the performance of the code by ScalaLife. The OpenMP thread parallelization should be automatically detected and turned on most platforms. Depending on the amount of processes involved and the speed of interconnects between the nodes; this version improves the performance by 0% to 50%.

2. Optimization of GROMACS performance on Blue Gene systems

2.1. Introduction

The special architecture of Blue Gene systems creates a number of challenges for those users wishing to optimize the performance of classical molecular dynamics codes such as GROMACS. The availability of tens of thousands of computing cores in particular inevitably leads to considerations of how the algorithms within the program can be best tailored to match the computer's communication topology. A crucial calculation to be optimised is that of the long range interactions which consist of dispersion-type particle-particle (PP) interactions and the electrostatic forces obtained from the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) method which makes extensive use of 3D FFT. On parallel computers these forces are obtained via a domain decomposition scheme which distributes the atomic interactions amongst the compute nodes assigned to the simulation. The PME component can be particularly expensive due to the need for global communication and this usually represents the limiting factor when using domain decomposition. To reduce this problem GROMACS versions 4 and above exploit the fact that the PP and the PME interactions can be decoupled and allows the user to assign nodes to perform only PME calculations while leaving the other processors to calculate the PP terms. Thus, by reducing the number of nodes doing PME, it is possible to reduce significantly the number of communication calls, a factor which should be crucial for massively parallel systems. As well as deciding the number of nodes to use for PME-only work, it is also possible for users to modify the partitioning scheme between PP and PME nodes in terms of MPI ranks with a runtime option. A further degree of flexibility is provided by the runtime environment of the Blue Gene architecture which can be used to modify the default distribution of MPI ranks amongst the compute nodes (we recall on the Blue Gene/P there are 4 cores/node) which on the Blue Gene/P system "JUGENE" at Jülich, in Germany, can be achieved with the *-mapfile* option of the

mpirun command. Thus, it is possible to analyze the effect of topology on performance for GROMACS without making any changes to the code, although in this work with the aid of the code developers we did make a small modification to allow the program to print out the assignment of MPI rank to physical node name. The aim of this study was to analyze these factors on the JUGENE Blue Gene system to obtain a set of optimal program or runtime parameters. In particular, we wanted to answer the following questions:

1. what is the most suitable topology on JUGENE Blue Gene system for the PP/PME partitioning?
2. what is the upper limit in terms of usable cores in this architecture?
3. why it's impossible to go beyond this limit and what are the possible directions for a future development?

2.2. Method

With the minor modification to the source code described above, version 4.5.3 of GROMACS was installed on JUGENE Blue Gene system with standard compilation and optimization options. To investigate the performance we executed a series of short benchmark runs, typically for 1000 time-steps, as a function of the number of processor cores n and varying the PP-PME partitioning scheme with the *-ddorder* parameter of the GROMACS *mdrun* command[2]. In this version of the program the *-ddorder* option can take three values: *cartesian*, *interleave* or *pp_pme*, the default being *interleave* which will distribute the PME nodes together with the PP nodes. The *pp_pme* and *cartesian* values on the other hand separate the PP and PME nodes. As well as the GROMACS option we also tried two possibilities for the assignment of MPI ranks in the nodes with the *-mapfile* option of the Blue Gene *mpirun* command. Thus, *mpirun -mapfile TXYZ* fills up each node with MPI ranks before continuing, while the default option *-mapfile XYZT* inserts one rank at a time into each node. We therefore performed up to 6 simulations for each processor cores count n .

2.3. Results

For the first set of simulations we used as a benchmark system a cubic box containing about 0.5M SPC water molecules. This was chosen since it is relatively simple but at the same time requires PME calculations; the performance data obtained for this system is given in Table 1. It should be noted that the number of nodes used for the PME was explicitly specified with the *-npme* option to be $\frac{1}{3}$ of the number used for the PP interactions. For this system size it was found that the maximum scalability occurs at $n=4096$ cores; in fact it is not possible to obtain data at processor cores counts higher than 8192 because GROMACS will not run if it is not able to create domains of least a certain minimum size (which depends on the input system and the options given to the program).

Since the scaling limit of GROMACS is reached fairly quickly with this system, and therefore of little interest for determining the influence of the partitioning scheme or Blue Gene/P topology, we decided to simulate a larger configuration based on an input from the standard GROMACS benchmark suite, namely the ion channel known as d.kv12. This benchmark contains about 120k atoms, and since we know from the water case that the simulation is unlikely to scale beyond 8192 cores, we created a larger system by replicating d.kv12 4 times in the x and y dimensions to give a model 4x4 membrane with 1.8M atoms (a benchmark which we named d.kv12_16). With this system up to 16384 cores can be used and the results are given in Table 2 and plotted in Figure 1. We note that in this case the GROMACS runtime was allowed to choose the number of nodes to use for the PME, except for one case ($n=8192$ cores) where the default gave a low performance. In these runs a value obtained by trial-and-error to give optimal performance was used instead.

	Performance ns/day					
	XYZT				TXYZ	
#cores	cartesian	interleave	pp_pme	cartesian	interleave	pp_pme
1024	1.739					
2048	2.355	2.356	2.549	2.365	2.552	2.400
4096	2.425	2.251	2.443	2.429	2.485	2.374
8192	1.332			1.382		

Table 1: Performance in nanoseconds per day (ns/day) for a system made of water molecules. A blank entry indicates it was not possible to find suitable domain decomposition for the given number of npme nodes

	Performance ns/day						npme
	XYZT				TXYZ		
#cores	cartesian	interleave	pp_pme	cartesian	interleave	pp_pme	
1024	2.908	3.040	3.051	3.120	3.262	2.805	448
2048	5.407	5.184	4.760	5.180	5.412	4.565	896
4096	8.393	8.387	6.919	7.777	8.684	6.393	1792
8192	10.170	10.170	7.821	8.503	10.534	8.197	4096
16384	10.548	9.100	-	9.580	10.716	-	6976

Table 2: Performance in ns/day for a system made of a slab of 16 ion channel proteins (d.kv12_16). A blank entry indicates it was not possible to find suitable domain decomposition for the give number of npme nodes.

Figure 1: Performance as a function of number of cores for various GROMACS pp-pme partition schemes and Blue Gene/P MPI rank mappings. See text for an explanation of the legend.

2.4. Discussion

Since the water box shows only a limited scalability, we will consider only the d.kv12_16 benchmark system. It can be seen that for a given number of cores the differences between the performances for the different partitioning schemes and Blue Gene/P mappings are small, although the TXYZ mapping with the ddorder interleave option gives the best performance at all core counts.

3. Parallel scaling of the OpenMP implementation

3.1. Introduction

Parallel versions of GROMACS up to v4.5 use MPI only to handle the communications between the processor cores. As part of the ScalaLife project, the code developers have released a hybrid MPI-OpenMP version (v4.6) where multithreading has been applied to the PME calculations and so may give performance increases on common SMP clusters. The aim of this work was to test version 4.6 by performing benchmark runs on the PLX Intel cluster at the CINECA supercomputer centre in Italy. This system has nodes with 48 GB of available memory and two 6-core Intel Westmere processors/node.

Additional tests were run at PDC Center for High Performance Computing on two different platforms. Lindgren is a Cray XE6 system based on the AMD Opteron 12-core “Magny-Cours” (2.1 GHz) processors and the Cray Gemini interconnect technology. At PDC we have 16 racks with a theoretical peak performance of 305 TeraFlops. Povel is a cluster consisting of 180 nodes each equipped with 4 six-core AMD Opteron 8425HE CPUs and 32GB DDR2 DIMMs. Network setup includes one 4xQDR Infiniband port per node for an approximate 2700MB/s interconnect bandwidth per node and a nominally full-bisection fat-tree Infiniband interconnect with two switch-layers and five roots.

3.2. Method on PLX Intel cluster

The hybrid 4.6 version of the code was downloaded from the site of ScalaLife [3] and installed on PLX according to the standard procedures given in the ScalaLife documentation and the GROMACS v4.5 manual. Simulations were run with the d.kv12_16 benchmark as described in the previous section (1.5M atoms). Two sets of runs were performed: GROMACS in MPI/OpenMP mode with 10 MPI processes and 3 threads per node and the same version of the program in mode “MPI-only”, i.e. with 12 MPI processes per node and no threads (we recall that on PLX there are 12 physical cores per node). For both the OpenMP and MPI-only runs the number of cores assigned to the PME was set to one quarter of the available cores, although the *npme* parameter for the threaded runs was also divided by the number of threads as described in the ScalaLife documentation. This scaling ensures that the number of “computational tasks” dedicated to PME calculations is the same for both sets such that performance differences should only be due to the different implementation, i.e. pure MPI or hybrid MPI/OpenMP.

3.3. Results on PLX Intel cluster

Performance data for the d.kv12_16 benchmark for the mixed MPI/OpenMP implementation and the MPI-only runs are given in Table 3 and Table 4 and displayed in Figure 2.

nodes	pme	ns/day
10	10	1.232
20	20	2.395
30	30	3.440
40	40	4.183

Table 3: Performance in ns/day as a function of number of nodes for the hybrid OpenMP/MPI version of GROMACS.

nodes	pme	ns/day
10	30	1.345
20	60	2.353
30	90	3.364
40	120	4.110

Table 4: Performance in ns/day as a function of nodes for the MPI-only version of GROMACS 4.6

Figure 2: Comparison of the hybrid OpenMP/MPI and MPI-only versions of GROMACS 4.6 on the PLX cluster

3.4. Discussion

With the exception of the value for number of nodes=10, it can be seen that the performance difference between the two versions of the code is quite small. This is consistent with the documentation from ScalaLife which suggests that the hybrid version of the code is only likely to show improvements compared to the MPI-only version at high node counts: unfortunately on the PLX cluster only maximum of 40 nodes were available for tests. In the next section we report results of a more exhaustive test of the hybrid code where a larger number of nodes are available.

3.5. Method on Cray XE6 (Lindgren) and AMD Opteron (Povel) systems

Both GROMACS versions 4.5.3 and 4.6 were compiled with the Intel C Compiler icc version 11.1. Enabling support for OpenMP required using CMake-2.8.5 for configuration of the build system.

Runs with 4.5.3 were done by scheduling the maximum 24 MPI processes per node. Two sets of runs with 4.6 were done - one with 24 MPI-only processes per node, and the other with 19 MPI processes + 6 threads per node thus allocating $\frac{1}{4}$ of the cores for PME.

Benchmarking models were provided by users of the ScalaLife Competence Center [3]. The examples represent model systems used in a real-life research work. They cover the most commonly used simulation sizes of ~40K and

~200K particles, as well as a very large 5M particle system. A description of each of the three model systems, Virion, KV12 protein and Lipid bilayer, is given in the corresponding results sub-sections.

3.6. Results on Cray XE6 (Lindgren) and AMD Opteron (Povel) systems

3.6.1. Virion system

The model system Virion consists of 5.1million coarse-grained particles used to study the dynamics of the envelope of a realistically sized influenza virion (84 nm diameter). This model uses shift potentials and not PME for electrostatic calculations.

As shown in Figure 3 the system on Povel seems to show a performance drop in 4.6 release but this is likely due to communication fluctuations and is not an issue. The virion system doesn't use PME and thus doesn't benefit from the special optimizations that were implemented in the 4.6 release.

The Virion system on Lindgren shows discrepancy in the performance for 4.5.3 version on 48 nodes as well as for 4.6 version on 24 nodes which is due to increase in MPI_Allreduce times. This is likely a coincidental peak in the network traffic.

Figure 3: Virion system performance on Povel and Lindgren systems for both 4.5.3 and 4.6 GROMACS versions

3.6.2. KV12 protein system

The model system includes ~100,000 particles modeling a protein embedded in a solvated lipid bilayer. The model uses PME for electrostatics and is depicted in Figure 4.

On Povel there is a clear ~10% increase in the performance with version 4.6. Much improved scaling when using hybrid OpenMP/MPI mode for PME. The hybrid mode is however slightly slower for small number of nodes, e.g. 1~4.

On Lindgren in version 4.6 the PME algorithm is faster but the network connection is also very fast so sometimes PME cores are idle. It's therefore recommended that users try different settings and manually specify the ratio of PME/PP cores in order to gain optimal performance.

Figure 4: KV12 protein system performance on Povel and Lindgren systems for both 4.5.3 and 4.6 GROMACS versions

3.6.3. Lipid bilayer system

The model system studied in this example consists of a mixture of single-unsaturated (18:0/18:1w9 PC) lipids, polyunsaturated (18:0/22:6w3 PC) lipids, and cholesterol, fully hydrated by water. The system contains about 40000 atoms.

The results of the runs are shown in Figure 5. As we can see there is a clear ~10% increase in the performance with version 4.6 on Povel, and much improved scaling when using hybrid OpenMP/MPI mode for PME. On Lindgren there is ~15% increase in the performance.

Figure 5: Lipid Bilayer system performance on Povel and Lindgren systems for both 4.5.3 and 4.6 GROMACS versions

4. Development of new adaptive symplectic integration algorithm with variable step size

4.1. Scientific and technical goals

For large atomic systems (106 atoms) the most time-consuming part of the simulation is the calculation of the electrostatic interactions. These are long-range interactions, so non-local, which necessitates the application of special algorithms for their calculation. In the most popular packages for MD simulations, different realizations of Ewald summation method [1] are used, as it ensures proper description of the long-range electrostatic interactions for spatially bounded systems with periodic boundary conditions. The bottleneck of these calculations is the FFT part. One possibility to improve the performance of the MD simulations is to employ integration algorithms with variable step size [4] for calculation of full electrostatics. In this approach the total force acting on each atom is broken into two parts, a quickly varying short range component and a slow changing long distance component. Since the long range forces are slowly varying they are not calculated at every time step, but at some bigger step. Limitations on the step size in this kind of integrators are severe, and are mostly due to stability than accuracy. The increasing size and complexity of the investigated objects presses strongly on the reconsideration of the existing algorithms not only because of the exploding computation volumes but also because of the poor scalability with the number of the processors employed.

4.2. Conducted investigations

We have studied the scalability and the work-load increase and distribution among the computing cores in the package GROMACS (version 4.5.3), on the example of three test systems with increasing size (5×10^5 , $\sim 10^6$ and $\sim 2.2 \times 10^6$ atoms respectively), with the profiling tool SCALASCA[5] and also by means of the GROMACS built-in tool `g_tune_pme`. We have also analyzed the stability and scalability of the existing integration algorithms with variable time-step implemented in widely used MD simulations code GROMACS in order to define the sources of the instabilities (different kinds of resonances). Based on this analysis, a symplectic time reversible integration algorithm specially designed for Petascale biomolecular MD simulations is under development.

These investigations were performed at the IBM Blue Gene/P supercomputer of Bulgarian National Center for Supercomputing Applications[6] (8192 computing cores) and on 32 computing cores of a local Linux cluster at the Faculty of Physics of the St. Kl. Ohridski University of Sofia.

4.3. Results

Our main results can be summarized as follows:

Up to 2048 cores, the three domain decomposition modes of GROMACS – *interleave*, *pp_pme* and *cartesian* – have similar performance, with slight prevalence of the default mode – *interleave*. However, on 4096 cores this mode has the lowest performance, the other two performing better, with a negligible difference between them (Table 5);

The GROMACS 4.5.3 performance analysis with the profiling tool SCALASCA shows that the *pme* cores which were taken to be $\frac{1}{4}$ of all computing cores, account for almost 40% of the communications, such a behavior being common for all three *dd-order* modes;

A study of the work-load and communication distribution over computing cores of the GROMACS executable with the profiling tool SCALASCA at a test system of about 460000 atoms on 512 and on 1024 computing cores (1/8 *pme* cores) showed that the average time spend by the *pp* cores is significantly shorter compared to the *pme* cores, that is consistent with the average amount of communications per core for the *pme* cores being essentially higher (by a factor of almost 2.5). The increase of the *pme* cores number would accelerate the calculation, but on the cost of having smaller amount of computing cores, involved in the calculation of procedures, that consume up to 65% of the total simulation time. Also, with the increase of *pme* cores number the total amount of communications increases, which may lead to a substantial slowdown of the calculation;

Analysis of short simulations (2 ps) with *pme:pp* ratios from 1:1 to 1:3 and cut-off radii from 0,9 nm (default) to 1,15 of a test system of 200000 atoms on 32 computing cores with the built-in GROMACS tool “*g_tune_pme*” confirmed the strong case-dependence of the most appropriate parameter set (Figure 6);

GROMACS appears to be less suitable for implementation of variable step-size algorithms, where an essential improvement of the performance can be achieved that way (Figure 7).

computing cores	ddorder mode	Interleave [ns/day]	pp_pme [ns/day]	Cartesian [ns/day]
512		6.672	6.592	6.600
1024		12.122	11.905	11.973
2048		20.856	20.627	20.426
4096		27.994	31.306	31.544

Table 5: GROMACS performance in the three dd-order modes.

Analysis of short simulations (2 ps) with fraction of *pme* cores $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{3}{8}$, $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{8}$ and $\frac{1}{16}$ of a test system of 460000 atoms on 128 to 1024 computing cores on the Blue Gene/P supercomputer of Bulgarian National Center for Supercomputing Applications with GROMACS 4.5.4 shows that the performance increases with the reduction of the number of *pme* cores up to 1024 cores where saturation is observed (Figure 6). Nevertheless, with the reduction of the *pme* only cores scalability drops, because of the increase in communication (Figure 7);

Figure 6: Performance of the GROMACS integrator as function of the number of PME only cores (shown as fraction from the total amount of cores).

Figure 7: The scalability of the GROMACS integrator for different number of PME only cores (shown as a fraction from the total amount of cores).

5. Conclusions and summary

In this work we have carried out extensive studies of the performance of several versions of GROMACS on a diverse set of computer architectures and with varying runtime conditions and program options. The aim has been to determine the optimal set of conditions for a given architecture and input, but without making changes to the code itself. In the first study on the Blue Gene cluster, we measured the performance as a function of the topology scheme adopted at runtime and the particle-particle and PME partitioning strategy used by GROMACS. It was found that although there are differences in performance at high node counts they are not particularly significant and are difficult to rationalize in terms of the options used. In fact these results illustrate the fact that on systems with very high numbers of cores, such as those of the Blue Gene range, the all-to-all communication scheme of the PME calculation will limit parallel scaling quite quickly. This does not mean that users should not attempt to optimize the run conditions on Blue Gene-type architectures, but rather that a priori it is difficult to gauge which set of conditions would work best.

In the second set of studies we investigated the hybrid MPI/OpenMP version of GROMACS as released by the ScalaLife project (version 4.6) where OpenMP threads are used for the PME calculation. We performed one set of studies on CINECA's PLX cluster comparing the hybrid version to the MPI-only version but saw little difference in performance. This was not unexpected given that the maximum number of nodes available for benchmarks was quite low (no more than 40) and that the internal network of this cluster (Infiniband) is quite fast. In fact, the ScalaLife documentation points out those differences would be most marked for high node counts or for clusters with low network bandwidths. To test the influence of the number of nodes and the interconnect, further simulations were performed on the AMD Opteron system Povel and the CRAY XE6 cluster (Lindgren) at PDC. It was found that the GROMACS version 4.6 release brings on average a 10% performance increase for simulations using PME method for electrostatics. For simulations that don't use PME such as the *virion system* the new release does not have any effect. The hybrid OpenMP/MPI mode however significantly improves the scaling of large systems on a large number of cores, typically >200,000 particles on >500 cores. On systems with very fast interconnects such as the Cray XE6 (Lindgren@PDC), the hybrid mode doesn't offer much advantage.

These investigations demonstrate that the increasing communications are the main reason for the performance deterioration of the MD simulation packages on large numbers of cores – typical for the case of petascale computations.

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